

Phase 3 - Workshop Protocol

Overview

This workshop explored how participants understand bodily vulnerability in the context of AI assisted healthcare, with a particular focus on patient perspectives. Through creative and material based exercises, the workshop aimed to surface experiential, emotional, and ethical reflections that may not easily emerge through verbal discussion alone.

Workshop Format and Setting

- Date and time: 4 December, 10:30 to 12:00
- Duration: 90 minutes
- Participants: 6 participants
- Facilitators: 2 facilitators
- Setting: In person workshop
- Materials provided: picture cards, keyword cards, paper, fabric, foam, tape, string, and other basic craft materials

Participant Recruitment

Participants were recruited through informal channels including word of mouth, Instagram posts, and WeChat groups. The recruitment strategy aimed to reach participants with diverse backgrounds and interests related to healthcare, technology, and humanities.

Workshop Agenda and Activities

1. Introduction (5 minutes)

Participants arrived, put on name tags, and had breakfast together. Facilitators introduced the workshop theme, objectives, and overall structure.

2. Icebreaking Activity: Picture Cards and Bodily Vulnerability (15 minutes)

Each participant selected an *image card* that they felt represented or resonated with the idea of bodily vulnerability. Participants then introduced themselves and shared why they chose that particular image. This activity was designed to create a safe and reflective atmosphere while easing participants into discussing vulnerability.

3. Prompt Exercise: “New Metaphors” (15 minutes)

Participants were invited to reflect on AI in healthcare through metaphors. *Metaphor cards* related to healthcare, technology, bodies, and care were taped onto a whiteboard.

Participants could either select existing keywords or write their own. They were asked to

connect these keywords to new metaphors describing AI in healthcare, focusing on bodily experiences and vulnerabilities.

4. Material Making Activity (25 minutes)

Participants worked in pairs to materialise their metaphors in the form of a wearable armour. The activity followed two constraints:

- The object must be wearable on the body.
- Only materials provided on the table could be used.

The armour metaphor was introduced as a way to think about how bodies might be protected, exposed, or transformed in encounters with AI systems.

5. Presentation and Group Discussion (25 minutes)

Each pair first explained their interpretation of another group's artefact. The original creators then presented their own work, elaborating on the ideas, experiences, and concerns embodied in their artefact. This was followed by open group discussion facilitated by the workshop leaders.

6. Wrap Up and Reflection (5 minutes)

The workshop concluded with a short reflection session. Participants were invited to share final thoughts, comments, or questions about the activities and the broader topic of AI and bodily vulnerability.

Phase 3 – Workshop Printed Materials

Metaphor Cards

Bodily autonomy	Self-care	Empathy	Healing	Protection and safety	The presence of AI
Trust	Power relations between people	Consent or dissent	Equity	Unwritten rules	Transition
Safety nets	Hope in technology	Fear of errors	Hierarchies	Fragility	Risk
Physical dependency	Invisible boundaries	Marginalized bodies	Data transparency	Machine-human collaboration	Your personal digital history
Algorithmic bias	Maintenance	Friction			

Image Cards

